

Input-state feedback linearization for stable radio-frequency magnetron control

Victor Etxebarria, Joaquin Portilla and Jorge Feuchtwanger

Dept. Electricity and Electronics, IZPILab Beam Laboratory, University of the Basque Country – UPV/EHU, Leioa, Spain

ABSTRACT

In this study, we propose a nonlinear control method to stabilize the oscillation of magnetrons. These power microwave devices have a complex dynamics, which can be modelled as simple third-order nonlinear oscillator. This circuit can be controlled using input-state feedback linearization, and the exponential stabilization of this scheme is proved. Simulations show that the open-loop model displays common properties observed in industrial magnetrons, such as noise and chaotic behavior, which can be removed and stabilized using the proposed method. The experimental results show that the control signal injected into the magnetron resonant cavities improves its performance, as suggested.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 28 September 2024
Accepted 24 March 2025

KEYWORDS

Nonlinear control; particle accelerators; magnetron; stability

1. Introduction

Magnetrons are remarkable power microwave generators that, from their origins, have proven to be one of the most important components in radar systems and are currently omnipresent in industrial and domestic heating devices. Their working principle involves the interaction of a cloud of electrons jumping from the cathode to the anode of the device together with a magnetic field. This spinning electron cloud trajectory induces electromagnetic fields in several resonant cavities at a certain main frequency. Although the device produces high-power microwaves, it is not a radio frequency (RF) amplifier, but a rather complex self-exciting power oscillator (Collins, 1948), whose behavior is not easily controllable.

Despite the advantages of magnetrons, such as their high efficiency, low weight-to-power ratio, and low production cost, they have not been widely used in practice outside radar and industrial heating applications. The reason for this has been their drawback when put into open-loop operation, leading to wideband unstable oscillations and spurious noise generation. Such a complex nonlinear device should be controlled to be usable in more challenging power microwave applications such as particle accelerators (Wangler, 2004).

RF power sources are expensive components that are essential to RF accelerators, from their ion generators (Feuchtwanger et al., 2018, 2019) to their RF resonators to energize beam acceleration (Feuchtwanger et al., 2022). These sources must be amplified to achieve

a sufficient frequency and phase stability. Tetrodes, inductive output tubes (IOT), klystrons and solid-state RF amplifiers have been used, but magnetrons have not been found to be suitable in the past because of their difficult control and stabilization. However, magnetrons have recently been considered a serious alternative to RF power sources for new accelerators. In particular, the injection phase-lock technique for resonant cavities has been demonstrated in industrial particle accelerators (Wang et al., 2024), but no general theoretical nonlinear control techniques have been introduced for magnetron devices yet. These can provide further powerful methods and valuable information to enhance the usefulness of magnetrons in real applications as the main research motivation presented here.

In this study, we apply input-state feedback linearization techniques (Isidori, 1995) to a simplified nonlinear model of a magnetron that incorporates the essential ingredients of its working principle. Many nonlinear control methods have been explored using complex designs, such as establishing sliding modes (Li et al., 2016) to control nonlinear dynamics, adaptive control for precision motion systems (Sun et al., 2016) or fuzzy control for stabilizing chaotic systems (Liu et al., 2017). Feedback linearizable systems have been considered for actuator failure compensation (Semprun et al., 2016; Yao et al., 2016), but the control of the nonlinear dynamics of magnetrons has not been approached using general nonlinear control techniques.

CONTACT Victor Etxebarria victor.etxebarria@ehu.eus

Dynamic linearization-based data-driven control can be used for some nonlinear applications (Hou et al., 2017) but avoiding disturbance has required observed-based control and back-stepping (Sun & Guo, 2014). Our approach to magnetron control includes general input-state feedback linearization capable of stabilizing the complex dynamics appearing in these devices whose real use has not been practical outside industrial heating. Robust stabilization of these devices using the new proposed technique may extend the magnetron use in important research and industrial fields requiring stable radio-frequency power sources.

In the control design of magnetrons we have proved that the proposed method results in an exponentially stable controlled system, and the simulations illustrate the good performance of the proposed control. The control signal applied in the simulation was also applied in the laboratory and the experimental results demonstrate how the magnetron can be controlled in practice. The presented theory, simulation, and experiment can explain the benefits of the injection lock method for magnetrons to be used as stable RF power sources for industrial particle accelerators.

2. State space simplified modelling of the magnetron

The dynamics of magnetrons are quite complex, because these devices include many key components working together, such as the filament, anode, cathode, magnet, resonant cavities, and RF antenna to extract microwaves (Collins, 1948). In terms of modelling such a device, but looking for simplification as much as possible, we need to include its main elements if we want to improve and control its performance not only for common industrial heating but also for more demanding applications such as particle accelerators (Kazakevich et al., 2018).

In terms of controlling oscillating circuits, ordinary voltage controlled oscillators (VCO) are typically modelled as second-order systems (Adler, 1946), which cannot explain most of the behavior observed in magnetron oscillations simply through feedback and negative resistance. The Colpitts oscillator (Maas, 2003) can be modelled as a higher-order nonlinear model (Cheung, 1985; Sarafian & Kaplan, 1993), including the basic nonlinear coupling between its voltage and current input. These basic components in a nonlinear higher-order system may explain most of the behavior observed in industrial magnetrons, including the main frequency, noise, RF instability and chaos.

Using the model of the Colpitts oscillator proposed by Sarafian and Kaplan (1993) as seen in Figure 1, we can

Figure 1. Model of Colpitts oscillator as simplified magnetron resonant system.

write its circuit state equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_1 \frac{dV_{C1}}{dt} - i_L &= 0 \\ Ri_L + L \frac{di_L}{dt} + i_L \frac{dL}{dt} + V_{C1} + V_{C2} &= 0 \\ -i_L + C_2 \frac{dV_{C2}}{dt} + V_{C2} \frac{dC_2}{dt} - N(V_{C1}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Since we can consider that the resonant cavities in the magnetron maintain their equivalent capacitance and inductance constant this allows us to assume that $\frac{dL}{dt} = 0$ and $\frac{dC_2}{dt} = 0$ so our nonlinear third-order model for the magnetron is simpler:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= \frac{1}{C_1} x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= -\frac{1}{L} x_1 - \frac{R}{L} x_2 - \frac{1}{L} x_3 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= \frac{1}{C_2} x_2 + \frac{1}{C_2} N(x_1) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $N(x_1)$ is a basic nonlinear coupling between the input voltage and current:

$$N(x_1) = a_1 x_1 + a_2 x_1^2 + a_3 x_1^3 \quad (3)$$

By means of this simple system we can explain most of the experimental effects measured in ordinary magnetrons, as well as to try to control their performance. Figure 2 describes the main components of a basic magnetron; therefore in the state model of the magnetron, C_1 is the capacitance between the anode and cathode, L , C_2 and R refer to the inductance, capacitance and equivalent resistance, respectively, of the resonant cavities. The three states of this system are the C_1 voltage ($x_1 = V_{C1}$), the L current ($x_2 = i_L$) and the C_2 voltage ($x_3 = V_{C2}$).

Figure 2. Basic components in a standard magnetron: (a) Filament, (b) Anode, (c) Cathode, (d) Magnetic field, (e) Resonant cavities, (f) Microwave antenna.

3. Practical input-state feedback linearization

The magnetron model (2) represents how it works as a nonlinear self-oscillating device without control. These oscillations may be unstable, noisy and even chaotic. We introduce here a practical input-state feedback linearization control scheme, which requires a control input variable u in the complete system as seen in next Equation (4).

Feedback linearization is a well-known theoretical nonlinear control method based on differential geometry (Isidori, 1995), the main idea of which is to algebraically transform the nonlinear dynamics of the system to be controlled into a linear system, at least partially. If this is achieved, then linear control techniques can be applied to obtain the required closed-loop performance. In practice, not all nonlinear systems can be controlled and the easiest way of applying this technique is for single input single output (SISO) systems whose equations are represented by:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})u \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g} are smooth vector fields.

The idea is to determine when these systems can be linearized by means of transformations between the state and input, how to find these transformations and how to design controllers based on this linearization. The basic steps we follow are based on well-determined differential calculations of the system to be controlled (4). These are:

- Construct the fields $\{\mathbf{g}, ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g}, \dots, ad_{\mathbf{f}}^{n-1}\mathbf{g}\}$ to form a distribution for our system.

- Prove the generalized controllability (i.e. full rank in the previous distribution) as well as whether it is involutive (i.e. all pairwise Lie Brackets of the vector fields in the previous distribution are themselves in the distribution). To apply the feedback linearization method, the main challenge is in proving these two properties.
- If both conditions are fulfilled, then our system is feedback linearizable, and thus we can find the first new state z_1 , by solving the following equations:

$$\nabla_{z_1}\mathbf{g} = \dots = \nabla_{z_1}ad_{\mathbf{f}}^{n-2}\mathbf{g} = 0; \quad \nabla_{z_1}ad_{\mathbf{f}}^{n-1}\mathbf{g} \neq 0 \quad (5)$$

- Then, we can find the complete new state vector from the first state z_1 , by means of the following formula:

$$\mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}) = [z_1 \quad L_{\mathbf{f}}z_1 \quad \dots \quad L_{\mathbf{f}}^{n-1}z_1]^T \quad (6)$$

- Finally the linearizing control law is $u = \alpha(\mathbf{x}) + \beta(\mathbf{x})v$ with:

$$\alpha(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{L_{\mathbf{f}}^n z_1}{L_{\mathbf{g}}L_{\mathbf{f}}^{n-1}z_1}; \quad \beta(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{L_{\mathbf{g}}L_{\mathbf{f}}^{n-1}z_1} \quad (7)$$

and v the desired linear control law for the new linear system constructed previously.

Differential geometry notation (Lee, 2012) was introduced to implement the feedback linearization methods (Isidori, 1995), which will be described next when applied in practice for the magnetron model.

3.1. Application to the magnetron

Considering the third-order model for magnetron (2), we attempt to find a feedback linearizable system so that we can construct a simple control law.

3.1.1. Control design on first state

First, we construct a simple nonlinear SISO system for input-state feedback linearization (4) with the following fields:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{C_1}x_2 \\ -\frac{1}{L}x_1 - \frac{R}{L}x_2 - \frac{1}{L}x_3 \\ \frac{1}{C_2}x_2 + \frac{1}{C_2}N(x_1) \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{C_1} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where we included a simple scalar signal u as the control input to the voltage $x_1 = VC_1$. It should be noted that the space state parameters in (8) will be considered known to design the proposed control law.

To determine whether this system is linealizable or not, we first construct the distribution $\{\mathbf{g}, ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g}, ad_{\mathbf{f}}^2\mathbf{g}\}$ where

$ad_f \mathbf{g}$ is the \mathbf{g} adjoint field with respect to \mathbf{f} or the Lie bracket:

$$ad_f \mathbf{g} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g}] = \nabla \mathbf{g} \mathbf{f} - \nabla \mathbf{f} \mathbf{g} \quad (9)$$

where $\nabla \mathbf{f} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$ and $\nabla \mathbf{g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$ are the corresponding Jacobian matrices.

In this case:

$$\nabla \mathbf{g} = 0_{3 \times 3}; \quad \nabla \mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{C_1} & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{L} & -\frac{R}{L} & -\frac{1}{L} \\ \frac{1}{C_2} N'(x_1) & \frac{1}{C_2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Thus, the Lie bracket let us to calculate the adjoint field:

$$ad_f \mathbf{g} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g}] = \nabla \mathbf{g} \mathbf{f} - \nabla \mathbf{f} \mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{LC_1} \\ -\frac{1}{C_1 C_2} N'(x_1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

and its Jacobian is:

$$\nabla ad_f \mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{C_1 C_2} N''(x_1) & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Thus, we can calculate the second adjoint field:

$$\begin{aligned} ad_f^2 \mathbf{g} &= [\mathbf{f}, ad_f \mathbf{g}] = \nabla ad_f \mathbf{g} \mathbf{f} - \nabla \mathbf{f} ad_f \mathbf{g} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{LC_1^2} \\ \frac{R}{L^2 C_1} - \frac{1}{LC_1 C_2} N'(x_1) \\ -\frac{1}{LC_1 C_2} - \frac{1}{C_1^2 C_2} x_2 N''(x_1) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Now the distribution we find is:

$$\begin{aligned} &[\mathbf{g} \quad ad_f \mathbf{g} \quad ad_f^2 \mathbf{g}] \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{C_1} & 0 & \frac{1}{LC_1^2} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{LC_1} & \frac{R}{L^2 C_1} - \frac{1}{LC_1 C_2} N'(x_1) \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{C_1 C_2} N'(x_1) & -\frac{1}{LC_1 C_2} - \frac{1}{C_1^2 C_2} x_2 N''(x_1) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

which is not involutive, meaning that the control field $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$ (8) we chose is not feedback linealizable.

3.1.2. Control design on second state

As a second choice, we can construct a simple nonlinear SISO system for input-state feedback linearization (4) with the following fields:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{C_1} x_2 \\ -\frac{1}{L} x_1 - \frac{R}{L} x_2 - \frac{1}{L} x_3 \\ \frac{1}{C_2} x_2 + \frac{1}{C_2} N(x_1) \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ L \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where we have chosen u is the control input to the current $x_2 = i_L$.

To determine again whether this system is linealizable or not, we first construct the distribution $\{\mathbf{g}, ad_f \mathbf{g}, ad_f^2 \mathbf{g}\}$. In this case, the Jacobians are the same as those in (10). Now, the Lie bracket allows us to again calculate the adjoint field which is now:

$$ad_f \mathbf{g} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g}] = \nabla \mathbf{g} \mathbf{f} - \nabla \mathbf{f} \mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{LC_1} \\ R \\ \frac{1}{L^2} \\ -\frac{1}{LC_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

and its Jacobian is much simpler that in the previous case:

$$\nabla ad_f \mathbf{g} = 0_{3 \times 3} \quad (17)$$

The second adjoint field is:

$$\begin{aligned} ad_f^2 \mathbf{g} &= [\mathbf{f}, ad_f \mathbf{g}] = \nabla ad_f \mathbf{g} \mathbf{f} - \nabla \mathbf{f} ad_f \mathbf{g} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R}{L^2 C_1} \\ -\frac{1}{L^2 C_1} + \frac{R^2}{L^3} - \frac{1}{L^2 C_2} \\ \frac{1}{LC_1 C_2} N'(x_1) - \frac{R}{L^2 C_2} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

And the new distribution we are constructing is:

$$[\mathbf{g} \quad ad_f \mathbf{g} \quad ad_f^2 \mathbf{g}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\frac{1}{LC_1} & -\frac{R}{L^2 C_1} \\ \frac{1}{L} & \frac{R}{L^2} & -\frac{1}{L^2 C_1} + \frac{R^2}{L^3} - \frac{1}{L^2 C_2} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{LC_2} & \frac{1}{LC_1 C_2} N'(x_1) - \frac{R}{L^2 C_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

which we cannot prove involutive; therefore the chosen control field $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$ (15) does not allow us to construct the feedback linearization.

3.1.3. Control design on third state

As a third choice, we can construct a simple nonlinear SISO system for input-state feedback linearization (4) with the following fields:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{C_1}x_2 \\ -\frac{1}{L}x_1 - \frac{R}{L}x_2 - \frac{1}{L}x_3 \\ \frac{1}{C_2}x_2 + \frac{1}{C_2}N(x_1) \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{C_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where we have chosen u is the control input to the voltage $x_3 = V_{C2}$.

Again in this case, the Jacobians are the same as those in (10). The adjunct field now ends:

$$ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g}] = \nabla\mathbf{g}\mathbf{f} - \nabla\mathbf{f}\mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{LC_2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

and:

$$\nabla ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g} = 0_{3 \times 3} \quad (22)$$

The second adjunct field is:

$$ad_{\mathbf{f}}^2\mathbf{g} = [\mathbf{f}, ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g}] = \nabla ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g}\mathbf{f} - \nabla\mathbf{f}ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{LC_1C_2} \\ \frac{R}{L^2C_2} \\ \frac{1}{LC_2^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

So the new distribution is:

$$[\mathbf{g} \quad ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g} \quad ad_{\mathbf{f}}^2\mathbf{g}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{LC_1C_2} \\ \frac{1}{L} & \frac{1}{LC_2} & \frac{R}{L^2C_2} \\ \frac{1}{C_2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{LC_2^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

which is trivial involutive because the components are constant, and linearly independent; thus, the distribution is full rank and general controllable. Thus the system (20) we chose is feedback linearizable.

To find the first component z_1 corresponding to the new space state \mathbf{z} , we must solve the following three equations:

$$\nabla_{z_1}\mathbf{g} = \nabla_{z_1}ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g} = 0; \quad \nabla_{z_1}ad_{\mathbf{f}}^2\mathbf{g} \neq 0 \quad (25)$$

Building the z_1 gradient:

$$\nabla_{z_1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x_3} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (26)$$

Considering the fields \mathbf{g} , $ad_{\mathbf{f}}\mathbf{g}$ and $ad_{\mathbf{f}}^2\mathbf{g}$ in (24) the previous equations are reduced to:

$$\frac{1}{C_2} \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x_3} = 0; \quad \frac{1}{LC_2} \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x_2} = 0; \quad -\frac{1}{LC_1C_2} \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x_1} \neq 0 \quad (27)$$

Therefore, z_1 is a function of x_1 . The simplest solution we can choose for these equations is thus:

$$z_1 = x_1 \quad (28)$$

Now, the rest of states can be obtained from z_1 :

$$\mathbf{z} = [z_1 \quad L_{\mathbf{f}}z_1 \quad L_{\mathbf{f}}^2z_1]^T = [z_1 \quad L_{\mathbf{f}}z_1 \quad L_{\mathbf{f}}z_2]^T \quad (29)$$

where $L_{\mathbf{f}}z_1$ is the directional derivative of z_1 along the \mathbf{f} direction:

$$L_{\mathbf{f}}z_1 = \nabla_{z_1}\mathbf{f} \quad (30)$$

which is the dot product of the z_1 gradient (26) and \mathbf{f} .

Thus, the new states are:

$$z_2 = \nabla_{z_1}\mathbf{f} = [1 \quad 0 \quad 0]\mathbf{f} = \frac{1}{C_1}x_2 \quad (31)$$

$$z_3 = \nabla_{z_2}\mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{C_1} & 0 \end{bmatrix}\mathbf{f} = -\frac{1}{LC_1}(x_1 + x_2 + x_3) \quad (32)$$

The linearizing control law is:

$$u = \frac{(v - L_{\mathbf{f}}^3z_1)}{L_{\mathbf{g}}L_{\mathbf{f}}^2z_1} = \frac{(v - L_{\mathbf{f}}z_3)}{L_{\mathbf{g}}z_3} = \frac{v - \nabla_{z_3}\mathbf{f}}{\nabla_{z_3}\mathbf{g}} \quad (33)$$

The z_3 gradient is:

$$\nabla_{z_3} = -\frac{1}{LC_1} [1 \quad R \quad 1]^T \quad (34)$$

Thus, from (20):

$$\nabla_{z_3}\mathbf{f} = -\frac{1}{LC_1} \left[-\frac{R}{L}x_1 + \left(\frac{1}{C_1} + \frac{1}{C_2} - \frac{R^2}{L} \right) x_2 - \frac{R}{L}x_3 + \frac{1}{C_2}N(x_1) \right] \quad (35)$$

$$\nabla_{z_3}\mathbf{g} = -\frac{1}{LC_1C_2} \quad (36)$$

so the control law (33) results:

$$u = -LC_1C_2v - C_2 \left[-\frac{R}{L}x_1 + \left(\frac{1}{C_1} + \frac{1}{C_2} - \frac{R^2}{L} \right) x_2 - \frac{R}{L}x_3 + \frac{1}{C_2}N(x_1) \right] \quad (37)$$

Because of the control law and diffeomorphism $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x})$ (29), we obtain the following set of linear equations:

$$\dot{z}_1 = z_2; \quad \dot{z}_2 = z_3; \quad \dot{z}_3 = v \quad (38)$$

Figure 3. Block diagram of the proposed control, based on input-state feedback linearization.

Once the state equations are transformed into a linear form, it is easy to choose a linear law ν for stabilization or trajectory following, because the equivalent linear dynamics are as follows:

$$z_1^{(3)} = \nu \quad (39)$$

To stabilize the system we define the error for state z_1 with respect to the desired performance z_{d1} as $e = z_1 - z_{d1}$. If we propose:

$$\nu = z_{d1}^{(3)} - \alpha_2 \ddot{e} - \alpha_1 \dot{e} - \alpha_0 e \quad (40)$$

then the closed-loop system finally is:

$$e^{(3)} + \alpha_2 \ddot{e} + \alpha_1 \dot{e} + \alpha_0 e = 0 \quad (41)$$

which is Hurwitz and thus exponentially stable with coefficients $\alpha_0 > 0, \alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 > 0, \alpha_2 \alpha_1 > \alpha_0$.

To illustrate as a whole the proposed control procedure and signal flow described in this section, a block diagram is shown in Figure 3. Note that as a pole placement design, the α_i parameters impact the control performance, but the above simple conditions guarantee stabilization.

As seen in the obtained control law (37), together with (40), the α_i parameters influence directly in the obtained closed-loop poles in polynomial (41). Note that the desired reference trajectory for the controlled magnetron will be a clean sinusoid oscillating at the nominal frequency of the device's resonators, so that the control enhances the magnetron's job. The disturbances and noise generated by the device may compromise the control performance, even though we can guarantee stability by placing the closed-loop poles as robustly as possible.

4. Simulations

In this section, we test the simplified magnetron model and control by simulation. The idea is to simulate both in open and closed loops, to verify the proposed ideas.

4.1. Open-loop magnetron

First of all we will simulate the dynamics of the simplified model of the magnetron (2) with $C_1 = 5.6\text{pF}$, $C_2 = 7.1\text{pF}$, $L = 91.4\text{pH}$, $R = 0.75\Omega$. The coefficients of nonlinear coupling (3) in the magnetron are $a_1 = 0.43$, $a_2 = 0$, $a_3 = -0.2$. These parameters are chosen to simulate the X-band (9.4 GHz) magnetrons used for particle accelerators (Yamamoto et al., 2007), to verify their performance.

Figure 4 shows the open-loop response of the oscillator, where the phase space (x_1 - x_3) trajectory is displayed, and the chaotic behavior of the magnetron is observed. The working principle of the nonlinear magnetron, without controlling its self-oscillating characteristics, is well substantiated by the proposed nonlinear model. Figure 5 shows the frequency spectrum of the magnetron, with a main frequency of 9.4 GHz. The expected noisy performance of the magnetrons is also observed. The results obtained reinforce the validity of the proposed nonlinear model of the magnetron, both in terms of the simulated response either in frequency or time domain.

Note that the phase state voltage simulation is able to display the nonlinear chaotic behaviour of the magnetron. The frequency spectrum simulation also displays noise, which is also a well-known property in magnetrons. Even though no noise has been artificially introduced in the simulation signals, its noisy dynamics does appear.

4.2. Closed-loop magnetron

Next, we present the simulation results of the controlled system by applying the theory explained previously. Our goal was to stabilize the oscillation around the desired state $z_{d1} = \sin(\omega_n t)$, where $\omega_n = 2\pi 9.4 \text{ Grad/s}$.

In Figure 6 the resulting phase-space trajectory is displayed and it can be observed that the magnetron is now well stabilized. The corresponding frequency spectrum in Figure 7 shows a significantly cleaner performance, which takes advantage of the efficient feedback linearization of the method as well as the regulation of the oscillation around a single nominal frequency. The control signal obtained from theory acts on the resonant cavities

Figure 4. Simulation of the open-loop magnetron: phase-space voltages.

Figure 5. Simulation of the open-loop magnetron: frequency spectrum.

through $x_3 = VC_2$. In Figure 8, it can be observed that, after a short transient, the control signal is essentially a sinusoid. Note that the injection of the reference sinusoidal signal into the magnetron, such as it is the case when applying the injection locking technique, results in a sinusoidal excitation of resonant cavities similar to the one explained before. So this provides an analytical demonstration as well as a physical insight of the

effectiveness of the injection locking technique for the control of magnetrons in particular (Choi & Choi, 2007; Tahir et al., 2006). The proposed input-state feedback linearization, as we see in the simulation, results in a control signal essentially the same as the injection technique in magnetrons. This provides an important result to explain the reasons why we can expect this idea to work in the real experiments we will test in the following section.

Figure 6. Simulation of the closed-loop magnetron: phase-space voltages.

Figure 7. Simulation of the closed-loop magnetron: frequency spectrum.

5. Experimental results

Open-loop magnetrons are operated through two power sources to energize the anode, cathode and filament. The basic setup of our laboratory is schematized in Figure 9. As shown in the previous sections, to stabilize the magnetron response, we injected the control signal into the resonators.

Figure 10 is a schematic of our laboratory experiment, which corresponds to the photograph of our setup as seen in Figure 11, for a standard 2.45 GHz magnetron.

Figure 12 shows the frequency spectra measured in laboratory experiments. The magnetron without control provides a decent microwave signal around its main frequency (spectrum shown in blue) but the response under control shows a significant improvement over a 10 MHz offset around this frequency (results displayed in yellow). The corresponding phase noise measurements have shown 30 dBc/Hz improvements in our experiments. Amplitude and phase noise, some of the most undesirable characteristics in power signals for particle accelerators, have clearly been improved now in the

Figure 8. Simulation of the closed-loop magnetron: control signal.

Figure 9. Schematic of the magnetron setup in the laboratory: PS2 for thermoionic electron generation, and PS1 for cathode anode jump.

laboratory. This experimental results allow us to consider magnetrons as a serious alternative of robust source of power radio-frequency and microwave signals for particle accelerators, instead of expensive klystrons, tetrodes, IOTs or power solid-state amplifiers. Magnetrons have not been used before in this context, because they have not been suitable for real control of amplitude, frequency and phase signals, which we can now clearly consider.

6. Conclusions

A nonlinear control method to stabilize magnetrons, based on input-state feedback linearization is presented. It has been proved that this method results in an exponentially stable system when applied to a third-order nonlinear magnetron model. Simulations have demonstrated that their common noisy and chaotic behavior can be improved using this nonlinear control method.

Through the proposed scheme, we also provided an analytical explanation to account for the benefit of the injection locking technique in magnetrons. The injection of this control signal into the magnetron resonators in our laboratory improves its performance and we have found that these devices can be used for demanding applications such as particle accelerators as well as for most autonomous circuits.

The main contribution of this work has been to propose and prove both in theory and practice the stabilization of the magnetron signals, based on a complete nonlinear feedback linearization control design. This approach has allowed us also to explain the injection

Figure 10. Schematic of the magnetron setup in the laboratory: injection of control signal.

Figure 11. Experimental setup: (a) Magnetron; (b) Circulator 1; (c) Circulator 2; (d) Injection port; (e) Load for backward protection; (f) Forward measurement port; (g) RF load; (h) VNA.

Figure 12. Measurement of the magnetron frequency response without and with control.

locking technique for magnetrons used in the laboratory. As potential future research directions, this promising starting point allows us to include further control loops in real magnetrons to precisely regulate the amplitude, frequency and phase of high-frequency power signals needed in particle accelerators.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This work was supported in part by the Basque Government [grant number IT1533-22] and [grant number KK-2022/00026]. It is also supported in part by the Spanish Research Agency [grant number PID2023-148792OB-I00].

Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author V.E. upon reasonable request.

References

- Adler, R. (1946). A study of locking phenomena in oscillators. *Proceedings of the IRE*, 34(6), 351–357. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JRPROC.1946.229930>.
- Cheung, W. N. (1985). Gain requirement profile of LC oscillators. *International Journal of Electronics*, 59(5), 629–636. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207218508920739>.
- Choi, J. J., & Choi, G. W. (2007). Observation of frequency locking and noise reduction in a self-injection-locked magnetron. *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, 54(12), 3430–3432. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TED.2007.908879>.
- Collins, G. B. (1948). *Microwave magnetrons*. McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc.
- Feuchtwanger, J., Etxebarria, V., Portilla, J., Jugo, J., Arredondo, I., Badillo, I., Asua, E., Vallis, N., Elorza, M., Alberdi, B., Enparantza, R., Ariz, I., Muñoz, I., Etxebeste, U., & Hernandez, I. (2022). New generation compact linear accelerator for low-current, low-energy multiple applications. *Applied Sciences*, 12, 4118–4118-11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12094118>.
- Feuchtwanger, J., Etxebarria, V., Portilla, J., Jugo, J., Badillo, I., & Arredondo, I. (2018). Hydrogen electron cyclotron resonance ion sources plasma characterization based on simple optical emission spectroscopy. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, A*, 881, 44–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2017.11.008>.
- Feuchtwanger, J., Etxebarria, V., Portilla, J., Jugo, J., Badillo, I., & Arredondo, I. (2019). New compact ion source design and implementation for low current applications. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, A*, 929, 101–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2019.03.052>.
- Hou, Z., Chi, R., & Gao, H. (2017). An overview of dynamic linearization-based data-driven control and applications. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 64(5), 4076–4090. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2016.2636126>.
- Isidori, A. (1995). *Nonlinear control systems* (3rd ed.). Springer-Verlag.

- Kazakevich, G., Johnson, R., Levedev, V., Yakovlev, V., & Pavlov, V. (2018). Resonant interaction of the electron beam with a synchronous wave in controlled magnetrons for high-current superconducting accelerators. *Physical Review Accelerators and Beams*, 21, 062001-1–062001-12. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.21.062001>.
- Lee, J. M. (2012). *Introduction to smooth manifolds* (2nd ed.). Springer.
- Li, H., Shi, P., & Yao, D. (2016). Adaptive sliding-mode control of Markov jump nonlinear systems with actuator faults. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 62(4), 1933–1939. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.2016.2588885>.
- Liu, Y., Park, J. H., Guo, B. Z., & Shu, Y. (2017). Further results on stabilization of chaotic systems based on fuzzy memory sampled-data control. *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, 26(2), 1040–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TFUZZ.2017.2686364>.
- Maas, S. A. (2003). *Nonlinear microwave and RF circuits* (2nd ed.). Artech House, Inc.
- Sarafian, G., & Kaplan, B. Z. (1993). A new approach to the modeling of the dynamics of RF VCO's and some of its practical implications. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Fundamental Theory and Applications*, 40(12), 895–901. <https://doi.org/10.1109/81.269030>.
- Semprun, K. A., Yan, L., Butt, W. A., & Chen, P. C. (2016). Dynamic surface control for a class of nonlinear feedback linearizable systems with actuator failures. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 28(9), 2209–2214. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2016.2572205>.
- Sun, H., & Guo, L. (2014). Composite adaptive disturbance observer-based control and back-stepping method for nonlinear system with multiple mismatched disturbances. *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, 351(2), 1027–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfranklin.2013.10.002>.
- Sun, W., Zhang, Y., Huang, Y., Gao, H., & Kaynak, O. (2016). Transient performance-guaranteed robust adaptive control and its application to precision motion control systems. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 63(10), 6510–6518. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2016.2542787>.
- Tahir, I., Dexter, A., & Carter, R. (2006). Frequency and phase modulation performance of an injection-locked CW magnetron. *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, 53(7), 1721–1729. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TED.2006.876268>.
- Wang, H., Jordan, K., Rimmer, R. A., Laut, A., Anderson, J., Thackston, K., Moeller, C., & Sadwick, L. (2024). Progress on magnetron R and Ds for industrial particle accelerators. In *15th Int. Particle Accelerator Conference IPAC24*, TUPR39 (pp. 1498–1501). <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-TUPR39>
- Wangler, T. (2004). *RF linear accelerators*. Wiley-VCH Verlag.
- Yamamoto, T., Natsui, T., Yusa, N., Dobashi, K., Uesaka, M., Higo, T., Fukuda, S., Akemoto, M., Yoshida, M., Takatomi, T., Kudoh, N., Tanabe, E., Nakamura, N., Morita, S., & Yamamoto, M. (2007). Compact 950 keV X-band (9.4GHz) linac X-ray source for on-site nondestructive evaluation. In *2007 IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference* (pp. 1–2). Kitakyushu, Japan. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IVELEC.2007.4283405>
- Yao, X., Tao, G., & Jiang, B. (2016). Adaptive actuator failure compensation for multivariable feedback linearizable systems. *International Journal of Robust and Nonlinear Control*, 26(2), 252–285. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rnc.3309>.